

NIVA WP 3 –INRAE interview

Date: 17 February 2021 - 10h 00 – 11 h 30

Location: Teams meeting

Stakeholder description

1. Organisation name: INRAE National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food and Environment
2. Person name:
3. Person position /role:

Removed for privacy reasons: research engineer (satellite images and landscape domain)

Removed for privacy reasons: research engineer (landscape domain)

4. What is the general purpose of the organisation?
 - To provide knowledge on Agriculture, Food and Environment topics
 - To advise policy makers, deciders
 - To assess the impact of public policies
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5. What are the activities related to agriculture in general? What are the activities requiring use of data about agriculture?

Many of our researches about ecology and agriculture require geographic data (maps, databases ...). We are big consumers of the French LPIS.

User experience – User requirements

1. What current IACS data do you need?
 - Reference Parcel

We used them before 2015 when the crop information was available only at this level. After 2015, the crop information is on agricultural parcels (finer granularity) and since this time, we have used only agricultural parcels.

We are not conducting many historical studies, so there is currently no use of reference parcels.

- Agricultural Area (and LC information)

There is not such feature type in the French LPIS. The agricultural areas with the detailed crop types are quite suitable for our national applications and we don't need the aggregated information about LC (arable land, permanent crops, permanent grassland).

However, some years ago, we had the idea to produce a Land Cover map in Europe from satellite images but some in-situ data was of course required. Getting harmonised data about agricultural areas was very difficult and we gave up quite quickly. Data even coarsely harmonised according to the LC classes of LPIS (arable land, permanent crops, permanent grassland) would already have been quite useful.

- EFA- Landscape features

We have strong interest for the grass bands between cultures or between culture and watercourses, for wetlands, for hedges.

Currently, from French LPIS, we get only the length of hedges but not their localisation though it would be useful to us (we can get the info from IGN, the French Mapping Agency).

- Agricultural parcels

Data on agricultural parcels with their crop type is key information for us. Our laboratory is producing OSO that is a national Land Cover product produced from satellite images. The LPIS data is used to build the classification methods; it is used both as training and as validation data. This OSO product is widely used by researchers, for environmental studies... For instance, OSO has been compared to the French component of the LUCAS product, results have shown comparable statistics. The Ministry of Agriculture is now envisaging use of our product in complement of field visits for the LUCAS production. The satellite images may complement field surveys, in time and in space.

The LPIS data with its detailed classification (around 120 values) is quite suitable, despite a few errors (but that can be managed). With satellite data, we can complete where there is no declaration. Currently, our main issue is that the French LPIS of year n is only available on year $n+1$. We have some negotiation with French Paying Agency to get the LPIS at autumn of year n (even if not fully consolidated). For last 2 years, we have got LPIS data of year n at autumn (year n) what is quite relevant for us.

We may also need more specific information. For instance, there is research on-going about the modeling of irrigation requirements on water resources (e.g. watercourses). It would be necessary to know the irrigation practices: type of irrigation, dates. We have done a classification of parcels if irrigated or not (from LPIS and/ or from satellite images). Data about irrigation is not reliable.

More generally, we are interested about getting information about the practices:

- Organic or conventional
- If there is intermediary crop and what is its nature (for carbon storage)
- Technical interventions on grasslands (grazing, mowing); however, the LPIS data are not very reliable; due to administrative constraints, there are confusion between temporary and permanent grasslands.
- Sowing time (and vegetation status): this is useful to assess the phytosanitary risks on neighbour parcels in case of an infected parcel and to help deciding if it is necessary or not to make treatment.
- what is done from crop remains
- soil work, etc... (if permanent grass in orchards and vineyards ...)

The LPIS data on grasslands is also useful for studies about assessing the resources conditions for animal breeding, the data is used to characterise the environment.

- Application

We are not interested by the administrative information of the GSAA application. Getting anonymised data is fine for us

- Beneficiaries

Our laboratory is not working with such data but profiles of farmers are of interest for other researchers in INRAE.

- Animals

INRAE has a laboratory working on this topic. We might be interested ourselves as data on animals may be useful to assess the pressure on grasslands, for studies about botanic diversity. Knowing the cattle quantity would be helpful.

- Quality & controls

For our OSO product, the general rule is to use LPIS as reference data and therefore to assume that everything is true. However, in practice, we don't use some values (crop types) as we consider them as not reliable. We provide quality information about our OSO product by the reliability percentage for each class and the confusion risk with other classes.

Knowing the quality of LPIS data (e.g. ratio of wrong declarations) might help us to understand some discrepancies (but this is not critical). More generally, it would be useful for anyone using LPIS as reference data to be informed about its level of reliability. Quantification of errors is necessary to assess the data accuracy. Getting statistics at department level (NUTS3) would be fine.

- Entitlements

This is not useful for our laboratory. We are not aware if this kind of data is used by other colleagues in INRAE.

- Payments

This is not useful for our laboratory.

2. What potential future IACS data do you need?

- EO monitoring

We might be interested by the provisory crop type maps coming from the EO monitoring process, it would be useful for instance for the phytosanitary risk assessment.

- Geotagged photos

This might be of interest to characterise the parcel, for phenology phenomena but data won't be exhaustive, we will just get random information.

- Agro-environmental indicators

INRAE is partner of NIVA and involved in UC1b so very interested.

Opinion about data sharing principles

1. What data do you think should be publicly available for use?

The IACS data that has been provided to get public funds should be publicly available. If data was provided by farmers without being mandatory to get payments, it is open to discussion.

2. What data do you think should not be shared and should only be used by Paying Agencies?

- What has made you feel this way/why do you think this way?

Data protected by GDPR. Data should be anonymised but it is possible to find the related farmer.

3. Who do you think most benefits from partially or open data sharing?

- Can you explain why you feel this way?

Researchers, local public services, environmentalists, anyone involved in spatial planning and development.

4. Do you have any idea about how the process of data sharing from farmer to wider stakeholder groups can be improved?

Our main concerns are the following:

- Getting LPIS data sooner (having LPIS data of a given year during this year and not having to wait until next year).
- More harmonised LPIS data at European level
- Having better LPIS data, more exhaustive and richer